

MANAGEMENT OF THE SYSTEM SCHEME OF AUTOMATION OF ROBOTIZATION PROCESSES

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Abstract.

Robotic process automation is now becoming digital technologies, but disruptive technologies are also widely available as software for rapid automation of manual tasks and sub-processes, as well as the control processes of the entire automation system. Unlike other process automation technologies, robotic process automation is lightweight and only enters the presentation layer of IT systems for simulation. human behavior can also be robotized. Due to the novelty and variability of robotic process automation approaches in the implementation of the technology, there are reports of up to 30% robotic process automation projects fail. To address this challenge, we use a design science research approach to develop a framework for robotics implementation and we will provide information about the stages of implementation of process automation projects. We've analyzed 15 real-life project reports to find out we developed a preliminary sequence model. Then, we conducted several expert interviews and We conducted workshops to validate and improve our model. As a result, we have illustrated in frameworks and graphic tables with variable steps that offer instructions with sufficient flexibility to be used in complex and creating enterprise environments in technological processes, as well as for small and medium sizes we took as an example the technical processes of companies. It consists of three stages: launch, implementation and calculations were carried out in scaling processes. They include eleven phases that are relevant throughout the project and continuously provides cycle duration covering individual projects. Together, they provide knowledge management and process support for robotic process automation implementation projects.

Keywords: Robotization, automation of processes, technical system in automation, robotization control scheme, methodology, automation system processes.

INTRODUCTION

Competing with digital technologies is the most advanced technology to date. Many areas of potential future predictors technologies are becoming an important task and business leaders are interrelated with technological process automation and robotization processes related to the success of their organizations. A few showed that the importance of technological processes is growing rapidly and digital technologies in achieving business goals organizations and production enterprises are using technologies in a wide variety of ways. The concept of digital transformation so far was primarily related to production processes, as physical robots have supported humans in manufacturing tasks and become important in technological automation. At the beginning of the digital transformation period, all efforts were mainly focused on and aimed at providing the highest quality to the customer the service depended on the technical system of technological automation. Currently, attention is increasingly being paid to

technological processes of robotization and automation, dedicated to the concept of digitization of operational and business processes and digitization itself covers service enterprises, including primarily, and manages the technological system, For example, finance, banking, insurance, marketing, accounting, public administration, logistics, and other areas. Rapidly changing market demands and rapid development of information technologies makes a significant contribution to modern evolution, and The concepts of management using IT tools will drive the development of technology. And this the process of robotization of production processes is still at the beginning seems to have potential for expansion and growth in companies. From this point of view in the existing literature on the subject, such robotization should be broadly understood as automation, business processes through extensive use "robots", i.e. software that replaces humans it is necessary to carry out activities and improve them. Robotic process automation should be considered as one of the digital transformation technologies and repetitive and in robotizing companies it is necessary to create a technological scheme of routine tasks. Like other advanced solutions, technological automation of robotics provides high efficiency. By programming autonomous software robots to replicate basic administrative processes, it integrates software, artificial intelligence and machine learning capabilities automation of manual tasks people serve to facilitate manual labor. It is necessary to develop a software robot control program developed with the help of technological automation of the robotization process. This tool allows you to solve many business problems. Next, the main features and advantages are listed the enterprise after implementing such solutions

Capability for robot-assisted personnel manage more processes, work more efficiently and fewer mistakes are made in data analysis and calculations are carried out automatically based on the technological system;

Periodic reproducibility, technological reproducibility over time and several system diagrams are presented in the quality control of many office processes;

Robotization of technologically facilitating processes of robotization from the most regular, recurring employees delegating tasks and demanding them more tasks as well as increased repetitive standardization there are opportunities to increase the efficiency of tasks to a higher level;

more time for employees to engage in activities work and problem solving; business processes technological stages performed ten times faster;

The rapid results brought by the robotization system scheme, can be carried out in organizations with technological debt;

Automation technological processes are checked and taken into account validation points according to a predefined set rules;

Seamless operation with multiple systems that interconnect many computer applications and systems (eg PDF, MS Excel, ERP system, PowerPoint etc.);

The case presented for the introduction of analytics;

The possibility of personalizing the solution for an individual user, obtaining accurate information from it Emails are answered with security procedures and data confidentiality is ensured;

Reliability of software robots as they always follow a predetermined workflow which increases process reliability and compliance;

Picture 1. Technical system in robotization.

Robotization should be considered as a bridge between manual and full process automation and a technological scheme of automation should be created. As one of the key elements of the industry, it is the next stage of transformation efforts and the level of technological system formation in companies. Although robotics software can be used in all industries, the biggest adopters banks, insurance companies, telecommunications and are utility companies. These organizations traditionally had many legacy systems; therefore they are it creates opportunities for choosing technological solutions of robotics to provide integrated functionality. Organizations can use this technology rapidly accelerate digital transformation initiatives by unlocking legacy value technological investments can develop. Nowadays, software robots can be standardized more effectively and this ensures that they can be used in a wider range of use cases, departments, etc. Entire companies and even industries are also by them combining bots into reusable and repeatable elements, both their application and their power significantly expanded. Because of this the versatile and disruptive potential to transform business processes, increasing the will of intelligent automation helps them move to the next level for value investments. According to the author, future-oriented business process automation will definitely depend on the development. Intelligent process automation, artificial intelligence implementation, workforce management, robotics and cognitive technological systems such as automation will further develop. Therefore, the literature conducted review and robotization technological analyzes allow review and this technology is not only as a trend, but mainly increases the opportunity for enterprises to achieve competitiveness and form the appropriate organizational culture. Get rid of the usual boring and repetitive tasks and waste their potential, employees are free to use their capabilities. After the introduction of software

robots enterprises, an interdisciplinary research field robotics appeared, mainly related to the advanced technologies of in terms of automation and robotization vshows their economic impact on organizations. Recently, the concept of automation of robotics has been expanded and to its compatibility with artificial intelligence, cognitive computing, process selection, and data analysis study steps were reviewed. The introduction of advanced digital technologies allows to redistribute the technological system of robotization from execution, repetitive and error-prone procedures in business processes that require more complex knowledge and value-added tasks are performed in processes at equal values.

CONCLUSION

Due to the robotization of processes, the possibilities of technology increase and solves problems for many different reasons. Some authors claim that robotics is an advanced social revolution, perhaps even the same as the information age or the industrial age. The main goals for this automating business processes increases efficiency and profits, as well as reduces overhead costs. The digital transformation of the 21st century will be robots and automation development processes. Therefore, it appears as a concept and class of automation in the robotics system and information systems are important. It creates a modern business environment where information is processed on an unprecedented scale. Although robotization is not going to eliminate all jobs, it is some jobs are expected to be affected. There is growing interest in the impact of automation on societies. This article describes the steps and tools included in the suggested parts method. It is applied to two real-life processes that form its basis our assessment is cited. The results show that the proposed method is suitable for av includes the issues addressed. Basically, it increases the accuracy of the process analysis is followed. Additional benefits include indications of this method Robotization also significantly speeds up the initial stages of process analysis. Nevertheless, the approach presents some limitations that are planned, mitigated as future work. First, the proposed method takes into account the log a single user interaction is considered. If multiple back-office computers are monitored, there may be different solutions, but each should be evaluated. For example, a procedure might be to define a process model for each user first, then there are opportunities to combine them into a single process model. Analysts are also sure of it Developing a digital transformation strategy encourages automation - thinking first becomes important Robotics is only one component of a broader intelligent automation platform for a company's future survival. It should be integrated with other automation technologies. Adopt an "automation first" mindset the first step to implement digital transformation in the company. Such an approach to the problem allows to develop the enterprise and provide services to customers work better and more effectively and efficiently. This relieves employees of mundane, repetitive burdens work, allows them to focus on solving the problem and eliminates value creation problems. Currently, IT technologies are widely developing in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies, is currently conducting scientific research on the optimization and automation of technological processes in mining processes, and the use of robotization processes in mining enterprises. Azizbek's interest in the technological activities of mining enterprises is very high. Otelbayev Azizbek's many articles about processes in mining enterprises were published in international magazines. Currently, Azizbek is promoting the use of the development stages of technologies in mining enterprises. which can further increase performance indicators. I wish Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute, good

luck in his work and scientific research. Azizbek's articles on technologies and technological processes in mining enterprises were published in international magazines. He is very interested in technological processes, currently studying computer systems management, applications used in mining enterprises. Azizbek is a 4th year student and has been following the processes in mining enterprises for a long time. He is interested in mining and loading processes, flotation and beneficiation processes, and the structure of metal melting furnaces in mining enterprises.

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